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iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

D3.1 – V2I Communication, Aerial monitoring and route optimization v1

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Report information

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ABOUT iDRIVING

iDriving, a 3-year Horizon-funded project, unites 17 European partners in a mission to enhance road safety. The project focuses on transforming urban and secondary rural road infrastructure through innovation. It aligns with the EU's goals for smart transport and actively embraces emerging technologies. Key areas of impact include enhancing driver behaviour, improving infrastructure safety, and empowering first responders. Through a comprehensive Safety Criteria Catalogue, innovative sensors, AI-based warnings, and a Digital Twin, iDriving paves the way for safer roads.

The iDriving consortium consists of the following partners:

No	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	EL
2	POLYTECHNEIO KRITIS	TUC	EL
3	AUSTRIATECH - GESELLSCHAFT DES BUNDES FUR AT TECHNOLOGIEPOLITISCHE MASSNAHMEN GMBH	AUSTRIATECH	AT
4	UNIVERSITE GUSTAVE EIFFEL	UNI.EIFFEL	FR

5	FUNDACION TEKNIKER	TEKNIKER	ES
6	INGARTEK CONSULTING SL	ING	ES
7	INFRA PLAN KONZALTNIG JDOO ZA USLUGE	INFRA PLAN	HR
8	ACCELIGENCE LTD	ACCELI	CY
9	NETCOMPANY SA	INTRA	LU
10	SOFTWARE IMAGINATION & VISION SRL	SIMAVI	RO
11	ALP.Lab GmbH	ALP.LAB	AT
12	MUNICIPALITY OF ALBA IULIA	AIM	RO
13	DRAXIS RESEARCH VENTURES ASTIKI MI EL KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIRIA	DREVEN	EL
14	PRAVO I INTERNET FOUNDATION	LIF	BG
15	DIMOS THESSALONIKIS	THESSALONIKI	EL
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Executive summary

Deliverable D3.1 presents the first integrated version (v1) of the technologies developed under Work Package 3 (WP3), which focuses on enabling advanced V2I communication, safety-oriented traffic management, early-warning applications, and UAV-based monitoring within the iDriving project. This report presents the initial implementation of the core system components, technical approaches adopted across the tasks, and the early prototypes now forming the foundation of WP3.

Task 3.1 has delivered the initial communication framework supporting low-latency and interoperable data exchange, together with early components of the Vocabulary Hub for semantic alignment. Task 3.2 has implemented the first prototype of the Intelligent Traffic Management System, capable of analysing real-time data and generating safety-enhancing traffic strategies. Task 3.3 has produced the first version of the mobile and in-vehicle applications that provide users with timely alerts and guidance based on live information.

On the aerial monitoring side, Task 3.4 has advanced the UAV sensing and embedded processing capabilities required for incident detection and infrastructure observation, while Task 3.5 has developed a functional mission planner for single- and multi-UAV coverage missions. These components integrate into the broader WP3 architecture, forming a coherent baseline for further development.

The work presented in D3.1 presents and establishes the technical foundations that in the near future will be improved, optimised, and validated in the next project phase, leading to the final release of WP3 technologies in D3.2.

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Glossary

CCC	Common Connectivity Catalogue
CPP	Coverage Path Planning
DARP	Divide Areas Algorithm for Optimal Multi-Robot Coverage Path Planning
DRAC	Deceleration Rate to Avoid Crash
DTA	Dynamic Traffic Assignment
GUI	Graphic User Interface
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
ISAD	Infrastructure Support for Automated Driving
ITMS	Intelligent Traffic Management System
SUMO	Simulation of Urban Mobility
TD	Total Delay
TDC	Tekniker Dataspace Connector
TraCI	Traffic Control Interface
TTC	Time-To-Collision
TTS	Total Travel Time
UAS	Unmanned Aerial System
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the deliverable

This deliverable presents the first integrated version (v1) of the solutions developed under Work Package 3 (WP3), which focuses on advanced V2I communication, aerial monitoring, and route optimisation for enhanced road safety. This document outlines the initial implementation, technical foundations, and early functional capabilities of the core WP3 components, including the communication architecture, traffic management mechanisms, mobile and in-vehicle early-warning applications, and UAV-based monitoring and mission-planning systems. D3.1 reports the progress achieved to date, describes the methodological and technological approaches adopted, and establishes the baseline upon which the final and validated version (D3.2) will be developed later in the project.

1.2 Relation to project objectives and WP3 goals

The work presented in this deliverable directly contributes to iDriving's goal of building an integrated, real-time, safety-oriented mobility ecosystem. WP3 plays a central role in this objective by providing the data exchange backbone, intelligent decision-support tools, and applications needed to generate real-time alerts, optimise traffic flows, and support incident detection and response. The developments reported in this report address objectives of the project, including enabling low-latency V2I communication, deploying intelligent algorithms for safety-driven traffic management, delivering early-warning capabilities to road users, and establishing autonomous aerial monitoring through UAV-based sensing and mission planning. By delivering the initial functional components of these systems, D3.1 lays the foundations for demonstrating how integrated communication, sensing, and optimisation technologies can support safer and more efficient transportation environments.

1.3 Document structure

This deliverable is organised into chapters that reflect the workflow and technical scope of Work Package 3. Following the introduction in Chapter 1, Chapter 2 provides an overview of WP3, including its objectives and the role of each task within the broader project architecture. Chapters 3 to 7 present the detailed progress of the individual WP3 tasks. Each task-specific chapter includes a description of the task, its objectives, the work carried out to date, and the next steps planned toward the final version to be delivered. Chapter 8 summarises the main results achieved so far and outlines the planned activities for the next phase. The deliverable concludes with references and annexes, where supplementary material is provided.

2 WP3 overview

2.1 WP3 Objectives

The main objective of WP3 is to establish a low-latency and interoperable communication network that enables advanced Vehicle-to-Infrastructure interaction for enhanced traffic safety and efficiency. WP3 focuses on the development of data-driven connectivity solutions, real-time monitoring capabilities, and intelligent on-site applications that collectively support proactive traffic management and incident response.

Specifically, WP3 aims to:

- Build a low-latency, interoperable V2I network, ensuring seamless and reliable data exchange between vehicles, roadside infrastructure, and UAV systems.
- Enable real-time traffic management and safety alerts through efficient data acquisition, fusion, and transmission mechanisms.
- Deploy UAV-based surveillance systems for incident detection, environmental monitoring, and on-site safety assessment.
- Utilize AI-guided UAVs to perform autonomous safety monitoring and decision support, optimizing response times and situational awareness.

The WP also integrates research on semantic interoperability, data sovereignty, and communication standards, referencing the ISAD (Infrastructure Support for Automated Driving) concept and the IDSA (International Data Spaces Association) architecture. As part of these efforts, WP3 includes the design of a Vocabulary Hub for standardized data exchange and the development of tools ensuring sovereign and secure information flow among all connected entities.

2.2 Tasks overview

2.2.1 Task 3.1 – Network Infrastructure Development and Asset Intercommunication

Task 3.1 develops the communication architecture that supports low-latency, flexible and interoperable V2I communication across all iDriving components. It focuses on integrating heterogeneous sensors and subsystems, ensuring compatibility with ISAD concepts, and enabling secure data exchange based on IDSA principles. The task also establishes the Vocabulary Hub to guarantee semantic interoperability and incorporates mechanisms to support data sovereignty across the ecosystem.

2.2.2 Task 3.2 – Safety-Optimised Traffic Management Using Algorithms for Diverse Vehicle Flows

Task 3.2 develops the Intelligent Traffic Management System (ITMS) that detects safety-relevant traffic conditions – such as accidents, congestion, or road works – based on multimodal sensor data. It applies advanced algorithms to assess the situation and propose traffic management strategies tailored to current conditions and different vehicle categories. The task enables the dissemination of routing and safety guidance to authorities and road users, supports dynamic traffic light adjustments, and facilitates rapid response actions to enhance network efficiency and safety.

2.2.3 Task 3.3 – Mobile and in-vehicle applications for early warnings

Task 3.3 delivers user-centric software applications for drivers and vulnerable road users. These applications operate either through in-vehicle infotainment systems or dedicated mobile apps, offering non-distracting, real-time safety alerts derived from vehicle sensors and Digital Twin data. The system provides actionable guidance – such as speed warnings or alternative route suggestions – and allows users to contribute observations on unexpected hazards. This bidirectional communication enhances situational awareness for all road users.

2.2.4 Task 3.4 – Aerial Surveillance in Incident Management and Maintenance Tasks

Task 3.4 develops the aerial surveillance component of iDriving using a mission UAV equipped with RGB sensor camera. The UAV performs onboard AI-based processing via NVIDIA Jetson hardware to detect objects and incidents in real time. It provides both raw data streams and processed intelligence to the communication system, enabling rapid deployment, mission adaptation, and effective support for incident management and maintenance operations.

2.2.5 Task 3.5 – Dynamic Resource Allocation for Optimised Safety Surveillance

Task 3.5 creates advanced path planning and mission-allocation algorithms for UAV-based safety surveillance. The AI-based service determines how to distribute UAVs across the monitored area by considering available assets, area size, and UAV-specific capabilities. The system supports automatic launch during incidents, near-real-time mapping and inspection, and optimised coverage by assigning paths that match each UAV's strengths, thereby increasing efficiency and responsiveness.

2.3 Summary of progress to date

Throughout the implementation of WP3, significant progress has been achieved in both organizational, coordination and technical development. Partners have

actively participated in meetings and workshops, ensuring continuous alignment with project goals and facilitating efficient knowledge sharing.

User requirements have been gathered and refined through close collaboration with use case leaders and technical partners, defining the basis for the development of interoperable and data-driven V2I communication solutions. The consortium has carried out extensive research and evaluation of tools and frameworks, including the DataSpace Connector, to ensure secure, low-latency, and sovereign data exchange within the system architecture.

Technical developments have advanced across several key areas. Simulation tools for routing and signal control have been developed using SUMO, enabling realistic and dynamic traffic management scenarios. Mobile and in-vehicle applications have been designed and prototyped, including a first version of the user interface for real-time monitoring and data visualization.

Furthermore, the iDriving UAV prototype has been constructed and successfully tested, integrating onboard sensors and processing units for autonomous operation. Research and validation activities have supported the development of UAV Coverage Path Planning algorithms, now integrated into the end-to-end platform. These efforts are complemented by a Kafka-based infrastructure, which ensures reliable data streaming and synchronization between vehicles, UAVs, and backend systems.

Additional research activities have focused on AI-driven 3D scene generation, path planning, and traffic reassignment, contributing to a robust technological foundation for advanced V2I safety applications. Academic dissemination has also been pursued, with a research paper submitted on UAV swarm inspection.

3 Network Infrastructure Development and Asset Intercommunication

3.1 Description

This part of WP3 focuses on the design and deployment of a communication architecture that enables reliable and low-latency interaction among connected assets within the V2I ecosystem. The task aims to establish a flexible, data-driven infrastructure to support advanced road safety technologies and AI applications.

Building on the Infrastructure Support for Automated Driving (ISAD) concept, the task addresses the integration of various communication technologies to ensure interoperability, data security, and efficient information exchange between sensors, subsystems, and modules.

In alignment with the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) architecture, T3.1 also includes the development of a Vocabulary Hub to standardize communication semantics and promote semantic interoperability across systems. Furthermore, specific tools are being developed to ensure data sovereignty and trusted data sharing, supporting the overall objectives of the iDriving ecosystem.

3.2 Objectives

The main objectives are as follows:

- Design and implement a low-latency, interoperable network architecture for real-time V2I communication.
- Develop the Common Connectivity Catalogue (CCC) as a reference framework for harmonized data transmission and communication standards.
- Ensure semantic interoperability through the Vocabulary Hub, aligned with IDSA principles.
- Promote secure and sovereign data exchange among heterogeneous systems, leveraging the Tekniker DataSpace Connector.
- Facilitate AI-based safety and monitoring applications through efficient and scalable data exchange mechanisms.

3.3 Current progress

3.3.1 Network and System Architecture

The V2I communication network is being built upon a modular, scalable architecture that supports interoperability and flexibility between connected vehicles, infrastructure, and UAV systems.

The Tekniker DataSpace Connector (TDC) plays a central role in this architecture, acting as the interface layer that enables data exchange between different system components while preserving security and sovereignty (Figure 1).

Demonstrations and deployment exercises have been carried out to validate the architecture, focusing on:

- Establishing HTTP-based communication protocols for data transmission.
- Conducting hands-on demonstrations of the DataSpace Connector's deployment and configuration, ensuring understanding and alignment across project partners.

Figure 1: Tekniker Dataspace Connector UI

3.3.2 Interoperability and Data Sharing

Interoperability is ensured through the integration of standardized protocols and data models. The DataSpace Connector enables trusted, bidirectional communication between vehicles, infrastructure, and UAV platforms by applying the IDSA reference architecture principles. In addition, the connector structures and exposes system capabilities through catalogues aligned with the ISAD model, ensuring architectural consistency and interoperability across subsystems

To support interoperability and scalable data sharing the following have been considered:

- HTTP-based data transmission has been implemented for stable communication between components.
- Work is ongoing to integrate Apache Kafka into the architecture, enhancing real-time data streaming and synchronization.

- Demonstrations and explanations of the DataSpace Connector operation have been carried out with partners to ensure a shared understanding of its role in the system.

3.3.3 Vocabulary Hub and Data Sovereignty

The Vocabulary Hub is being designed as a semantic layer that ensures consistent interpretation of exchanged data across systems and services. It will enable unified data representation, reducing heterogeneity in communication between vehicles, infrastructure, and UAVs.

In parallel, the DataSpace Connector provides the technical foundation for data sovereignty, guaranteeing that data owners retain full control over the access and usage of their information.

3.3.4 Current progress summary

Overall, the team defined the architecture and design of the Common Connectivity Catalogue, following the ISAD model to structure and expose system components and capabilities, and implemented the HTTP communication protocols required for data exchange between system components. Demonstrations and deployment tests of the TDC were carried out, including detailed explanations of its configuration, operation, and relevance to the project's use cases. In parallel, work began on integrating Apache Kafka to support the management of high-frequency, real-time data flows.

3.4 Next steps

In the next phase, Kafka integration within the communication architecture will be finalised to enhance real-time data streaming capabilities. Integration of the DataSpace Connector into the broader system environment will continue, ensuring seamless interoperability with other components. In parallel, development of the Vocabulary Hub will progress further to strengthen semantic alignment and support fully standardised communication.

4 Safety Optimised Traffic Management

4.1 Description

This part of WP3 focuses on developing an Intelligent Traffic Management System (ITMS) designed to enhance traffic flow and improve road safety for all users of the traffic network who are making use of the iDriving platform. The ITMS will receive current and historical data on traffic characteristics (e.g. vehicular density, average speed or flow at specific locations), planned maintenance works and real-time information on detected or predicted incidents (e.g. traffic accidents, sudden infrastructure failure or extreme weather events) that may pose safety risks to specific user groups (e.g. two-wheelers, maintenance workers, pedestrians at busy intersections). This information will then be processed by advanced algorithms to formulate and implement traffic management strategies that alleviate congestion and ensure safety under current conditions. These strategies include: i) personalized and general re-routing suggestions for vehicles, providing appropriate alternative routes based on vehicle type, as well as fastest routing guidance for emergency and service vehicles (Route Guidance tool); and ii) adaptive traffic signal control, using state-of-the-art controllers to maximize junction throughput and minimize delays (Signal Control tool). The ITMS aims to improve traffic performance and increase system safety, both under routine congestion and during unpredicted or forecasted hazardous conditions.

4.2 Objectives

The main objectives of the task are the development, testing, and validation of the ITMS, which comprises two distinct tools: the Route Guidance tool and the Signal Control tool. The system will be implemented as modular code components within the open-source traffic simulation environment SUMO (Simulation of Urban Mobility). The task also includes the development of a communication framework between the ITMS and the associated iDriving platform components, enabling the transmission of outputs – such as re-routing recommendations and alerts – to the system’s control centre and the digital twin. Furthermore, the task involves conducting offline simulations for a range of potential incident scenarios for each Pilot Use Case (PUC) using historical demand data, and the subsequent generation and storage of results, which can be accessed during real-time pilot executions. Finally, the performance assessment of the ITMS will be carried out using specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), evaluating both the system’s operational characteristics and the improvements achieved in traffic flow and safety across the traffic network.

4.3 Current progress

This section provides a detailed description of the progress of the task towards meeting its objectives during the first 18 months of iDriving project. The development process of ITMS, composed of the Route Guidance Tool and the Signal Control Tool, is presented here as a sequence of development phases from the beginning of the task (M3) until today (M18), from the initial concept and design to the first trial deployment of the system in a synthetic network. The methodological structure of each tool is described first and the implementation part follows with some indicatory results generated from synthetic networks.

4.3.1 Route Guidance Tool (MBL)

The route guidance tool is designed as a traffic management system to provide alternative route recommendations for different vehicle types within the traffic network, aiming to improve overall traffic performance in terms of flow, travel time (delay) and safety. This is particularly relevant in the presence of unpredicted, potentially hazardous incidents such as traffic accidents, sudden infrastructure failures (e.g. pavement cracks, potholes, falling trees, landslides etc.) that obstruct vehicular traffic in specific locations, as well as during planned road maintenance works (road closure and traffic diversions) or high-risk predicted weather events that may pose safety concerns for vulnerable road users (e.g. motorbikes and bicycles on icy or slippery roads, heavy hailstorms or strong winds).

The tool is intended to mitigate traffic congestion and gridlocks while enhancing safety for all users, particularly during hazardous incidents. It achieves this by providing drivers with timely information and warnings about potential risks and guiding them towards safer alternative routes.

4.3.1.1 Concept and Design Phase

The design phase of the tool was preceded by an extensive review of the current literature and the State-of-the-Art approaches in path planning under traffic congestion and from a traffic safety perspective. This review covered classical shortest-path algorithms such as Dijkstra's and A*, as well as their dynamic and stochastic extensions that account for time-varying traffic conditions. Recent research also highlights the use of heuristic and metaheuristic approaches (e.g., genetic algorithms, ant colony optimization) and reinforcement learning for adaptive rerouting in real-time simulations. By examining these methodologies, the study identified gaps in existing systems—particularly the limited integration of safety indicators, driver behaviour, and incident risk assessment—informing the development of a more balanced, safety-optimized rerouting framework.

The integration framework for both of ITMS tools was decided after discussions between the main developing partners of the tools (MBL and TUC). Both tools were decided to be developed as modular code components embedded within the traffic simulation environment of SUMO (Simulation of Urban Mobility). SUMO is an

open-source, highly portable, microscopic and dynamic traffic simulation package, designed to handle large road networks. It provides a comprehensive platform for modelling, simulating and analysing vehicular and pedestrian traffic dynamics. Therefore, it enables realistic simulation of the traffic evolution in any urban or suburban road network of which a digital model can be built, and relevant traffic flow data can become available. Moreover, it supports multi-modal traffic simulation, by allowing the integration of different types of vehicles (cars, buses, bicycles, motorcycles, trucks, emergency/service vehicles and pedestrians) within a single network. Hence, its flexibility enables users to model real-world traffic scenarios, test and compare various traffic management strategies and evaluate new mobility concepts, like connected drivers and autonomous vehicles.

4.3.1.2 Methodological approach and technical framework

The main concept of route guidance is to provide users with a complete path, in the form of a sequence of adjacent roads (i.e. a route) connecting a given origin point to a given destination point, usually with the objective that the trip be completed in the shortest possible time or by covering the shortest possible distance. However, these objectives are often not simultaneously achieved by the same route, especially in cases of increased levels of traffic congestion, where the crossing time of each road in each network differs significantly from the one estimated by assuming that vehicles move with free-flow speed (without delays owed to the presence of other vehicles). When congestion has formed within a network, a distance-wise longer path may be a faster option for the completion of a trip because the shortest-distance path may be congested, thus allowing much smaller moving speed and inflicting delays. Usually, drivers choose their selected path based on either shortest distance - if they have no empirical knowledge of the current traffic conditions - or based on shortest travel time even if they need to travel longer distance, if they are frequent commuters and have knowledge of the typical traffic congestion patterns of the network.

However, more users nowadays rely on routing apps for the path planning of their daily trips. This fact can provide significant leverage to traffic managers to intervene and alter the distribution of traffic within a road network, aiming to achieve better use of its capacity, thus leading to reduced congestion-related delays and increased fluidity during peak times. This advantage becomes even more important in the event of a sudden incident, like a traffic accident, a land slide or fallen tree, which can block one or more lanes of a street, and lead to formation of queues and severe delays if the current traffic density is high. This is the main idea that the Route Guidance tool for iDriving aims to bring to life, while considering the State-of-the-Art methods for path planning and with a special focus on the safety side. On this ground, the path planning mechanism of the tool is built on the rationale of shortest-path algorithms, but using a generalized weighted cost of travelling for each road (link or edge) of the traffic network which considers the vehicle type, current traffic conditions as well as safety criteria, instead of using just

the length (distance) of the road and the average (or free-flow) speed for each vehicle.

More specifically, a weighted link cost function is constructed to respond to the requirements of the route guidance tool, which estimates the generalized travel cost for every road segment (link) of the network as a weighted sum of four key components:

- Expected travel time, derived from the currently observed average speed per vehicle type
- Safety distance from localized reported incidents (e.g. accidents, tree falls, potholes etc.) blocking traffic or causing bottlenecks
- Penalty cost component for the cases of roads that are completely closed to traffic (e.g. planned maintenance)
- Additional cost component associated with adverse weather conditions affecting some of all vehicle types in different degree (e.g. motorcycles and bicycles for the cases of gusty winds)

The mathematical formulation of the above function is given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_z(v_z, lev, L_z, veh) &= \beta_1 \frac{L_z}{v_z} \\
 &+ \sum_i [\beta_2 b_{acc,i} D_{acc} H_{acc}(veh, lev) + \beta_3 b_{mnt,i} H_{mnt}(veh, lev) \\
 &+ \beta_4 b_{w,i} H_w(veh, lev)]_{alert_i}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$D_{acc} = \begin{cases} (M_d - d_a), & \text{if } M_d \geq d_a \\ 0, & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

$$d_a = \sqrt{(e_{zx} - l_x)^2 + (e_{zy} - l_y)^2}$$

$$H_{inc} = b_{veh} lev, \quad \forall inc \in \{acc, mnt, w\}$$

In the above formula f_z indicates the generalized cost of road segment (link) z , which is a function of the most recently observed average speed of vehicles in link z ; L_z denotes the length of road segment z ; lev is a weighting parameter that indicates the level of intensity - in terms of safety risk - of the reported incident; veh denotes the vehicle type for which the cost is estimated (e.g. car, bicycle, truck, motorcycle etc.); $b_{acc,i}$, $b_{mnt,i}$, $b_{w,i}$ are binary variables indicating the type of incident

inc (“accident”, “maintenance” or “weather” respectively) that is reported by alert i ; H_{inc} is a penalty cost factor reflecting the intensity level lev of the incident of type inc on vehicles of type veh , which is quantified by weighting factor b_{veh} ; β_j with j from 1 to 4 are pre-set weighting factors that are used to indicate the importance of each term in the generalized cost estimation; D_{acc} is the penalty factor for the links that are in the proximity of the incident location; d_a is the Euclidian distance between the accident location (with coordinates l_x and l_y) and the starting node of link z (with coordinates $e_{z,x}$ and $e_{z,y}$, respectively); and M_d is the preset maximum distance within which the proximity-to-incident penalty factor applies. The first cost term corresponds to the estimated travel time given the latest average speed in the road segment, which considers the current traffic conditions; the second term corresponds to the penalty cost stemming from the proximity of the road to the location of a reported “accident”; the third term refers to the penalty cost induced by closure of the road due to “maintenance” works; and the fourth term refers to the cost related to extreme “weather” conditions. For each alert, only one of the three last terms is non-zero. If several alerts are active simultaneously, the cost terms of each alert are aggregated with the sum factor.

By estimating the generalized cost of traveling in all road segments of the network and for each different vehicle type, a shortest-path algorithm can identify the best (lowest-cost) path for any origin-destination pair, assuming knowledge of the current traffic conditions in the network (e.g. latest observed average speed in every link). By re-calculating all paths in regular time intervals during the simulation and assigning them to vehicles, a simulation-based dynamic user equilibrium is approximated. This process is known as Dynamic Traffic Assignment (DTA).

Figure 2: Simulation process within SUMO integrating the route guidance tool

The integration of the route guidance tool with the main SUMO processes is conducted through SUMO’s external API, TraCI (Traffic Control Interface), which allows for real-time interaction and co-simulation with additional systems (e.g. communication simulators, energy models etc.). The code is written in Python. The outline of the rerouting process is described in algorithmic form in Figure 2.

4.3.1.3 Use Case configuration, Implementation and Outcomes

Given the lack of available digital models and real traffic data for the project’s PUCs during the first phase of iDriving, the initial development and testing of the routing tool was done on a synthetic network that was created using suitable SUMO functions. A demand scenario leading to moderate congestion was randomly created and fixed-time traffic signal settings were automatically assigned to all junctions using existing SUMO tools, respectively. The demand scenario consists of different vehicle types (cars, buses, motorbikes, trucks). The constructed synthetic network is shown in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: A synthetic traffic network used during the development and testing of the tool.

Building the setup of this synthetic network allowed for a fast kick-off of the initial development, debugging, validation and functionality testing of the route guidance tool under controlled conditions. It also allowed for documenting all the requirements for constructing the SUMO model and simulation setup for the upcoming PUCs, such as the need for historical travel demand data and traffic signal settings.

Due to various limitations related to real-time data and signal settings availability, the required computational time of simulation and the availability of all related infrastructure during the pilot test cases execution, the operation of both routing and signal control tools will happen in principle offline, where numerous potential incident scenarios of all types and according to the description of each case study will be created and simulated in many critical roads of each network. Historical demand data (where available) will be used to configure each simulation test and traffic signal settings will be automatically assigned by the respective SUMO functions to all intersections, unless the real signal plans are made available by the corresponding authorities. The results of all tested scenarios will be stored and tagged accordingly, so that they can easily be retrieved from the database, in case a similar scenario is identified during the real-time pilot executions.

During the process of testing the functioning of the route guidance tool, a library of potential events triggering a safety alert in the network is created for different locations of the synthetic network, replicating a complete use case. The same process will be followed to a larger extent also for the PUCs of the project. A table with the list of tested incident scenarios and their characteristics is given below (Table 1). An accompanying map of the network indicating the affected locations for each scenario is also provided (Figure 4).

Table 1: List of test scenarios for the synthetic network

filename	type	vehTypes	coordinates	AdditionalClosureLinkIDs	EmergencyVehicles_Locations
alert_scenario_001.json	accident	['car','bike','truck']	[855.7, 901.4]	[]	['-1474','-338','-2182','-2251']
alert_scenario_002.json	accident	['car','bike','truck']	[1301.06, 958.82]	[]	['-1474','-338','-2182','-2251']
alert_scenario_003.json	accident	['car','bike','truck']	[1128.02, 1401.74]	[]	['-1474','-338','-2182','-2251']
alert_scenario_004.json	accident	['car','bike','truck']	[1101.74, 1339.81]	[]	['-1474','-338','-2182','-2251']
alert_scenario_005.json	accident	['car','bike','truck']	[853.96, 1352.07]	[]	['-1474','-338','-2182','-2251']
alert_scenario_006.json	maintenance	['car','bike','truck']	[]	['190','-184','-2020','-190','184','2020']	['-1474','-338','-2182','-2251']
alert_scenario_007.json	maintenance	['car','bike','truck']	[]	['184','-184','172','-172']	['-1474','-338','-2182','-2251']
alert_scenario_008.json	maintenance	['car','bike','truck']	[]	['60','-60','75','-75','64','-64']	['-1474','-338','-2182','-2251']
alert_scenario_009.json	maintenance	['car','bike','truck']	[]	['75','-75','162','-162','164','-164','60','-60','64','-64']	['-1474','-338','-2182','-2251']
alert_scenario_010.json	weather	['car','bike','truck']	[]	['190','-184','-2020','-190','184','2020']	['-1474','-338','-2182','-2251']
alert_scenario_011.json	weather	['car','bike','truck']	[]	['184','-184','172','-172']	['-1474','-338','-2182','-2251']

Figure 4: Locations of incidents of test scenarios on the network map. Each colour represents an incident type.

Each scenario is described by its type (accident, maintenance, weather etc.), the vehicle types the incident affects, the coordinates of the incident occurrence (if it is localised in one point), an additional set of road segments that are affected by the incident (e.g. closure for maintenance or weather conditions which are not localised to a specific point), and the pre-set waiting locations of emergency vehicles. The information concerning each incident is described in a *.json* file, which is read by the system, once it becomes available (incident is detected).

Traffic simulation for the synthetic network with the randomly generated multi-modal demand was performed for the case of no incident alert occurring, as well as for each one of the incident scenarios of Table 1. For each case, the simulation time is two hours, which corresponds to a typical morning peak, and each alert is active for one hour. The routing tool is producing informative alerts and recommended path adjustments using the proposed link cost function, as well as fastest routes for emergency vehicles for the incident location. Each scenario is compared to the case where no routing suggestions are sent and after links closure, drivers are assigned the distance-wise shortest path to adapt their trips (done by default in SUMO). In Figure 5 below, we can see snapshots of the simulation runs, for scenarios 4 and 5 (accidents), where queues are formed in different parts of the network after the affected links closure (shown in orange). Figure 6 shows the difference in the use of road segments before and after the incident, when the updated routes are considered. In this way, the aggregated rerouting suggestions indicate which roads are mostly suggested as alternatives in each case.

Figure 5: Snapshots from simulation of scenarios 4 (left) and 5 (right)

Figure 6: Change in road usage induced by the route guidance tool (all vehicle types). Red highlights heavier use and blue lighter use. Orange square depicts the closed link. Scenario 4 (left) and scenario 5 (right).

The results set that is generated and stored into a database for each scenario includes the following set of files (Figure 7):

- Generated alerts for all drivers (can be sent to control centre, VMS or in user apps)
- Old and updated routes of re-routed vehicles (including origin, destination and vehicle type)
- KPIs for performance evaluation (total number of trips, average travel time, average delay, total number of rerouted vehicles, average and percentage of high TTC and DRAC, and total CO₂ emissions)

res_scenario_005_alerts						
generated alerts						
Attention! accident on -219 . Access forbidden. Take 60 and 31 for car, 60 and 214 for bike, 60 and 31 for truck, instead.						201.0
Attention! accident on -219 . Access forbidden. Take 60 and 31 for car, 60 and 214 for bike, 60 and 31 for truck, instead.						1101.0
Attention! accident on -219 . Access forbidden. Take 60 and 31 for car, 60 and 214 for bike, 60 and 31 for truck, instead.						2001.0
Attention! accident on -219 . Access forbidden. Take 60 and 31 for car, 60 and 214 for bike, 60 and 31 for truck, instead.						2901.0
Alert expired. Road -219, open again.						3800.0

res_scenario_005_reroutes						
vehicle type	veh ID	origin	destination	alternative_path		
car	t118	-79	-2199	(-79', '75', '162', '-164', '172', '196', '-1956', '1960', '2199', '-2199')		
car	t2689	2284	-1939	('2284', '-2283', '-1775', '-474', '462', '-1992', '-184', '196', '-1956', '-1940', '1946', '-1951', '-1939')		
car	t2882	-2316	1737	(-2316', '2284', '-2283', '-1775', '-474', '-206', '-5', '11', '23', '31', '60', '79', '-844', '854', '1002', '-1470', '1474', '1722', '1737')		
car	t3440	1960	-1470	('1960', '-1987', '-1950', '1939', '-1747', '-1597', '-1242', '-1168', '-1148', '1150', '1194', '-1470')		
car	t3800	-1775	-92	(-1775', '-474', '-206', '-5', '11', '23', '31', '60', '92', '214', '-214', '-92')		
car	t5074	-1777	2182	(-1777', '-214', '-92', '75', '162', '-164', '172', '184', '1994', '2182')		
car	t5194	-58	-190	(-58', '64', '162', '-164', '172', '196', '-583', '-229', '-190')		
car	t5877	1722	196	('1722', '-1492', '-1469', '1470', '-1002', '-854', '844', '-79', '75', '162', '-164', '172', '196')		

res_scenario_005_ev_routes						
veh_type	veh_ID	start_edge	destination_edge	fastest_route	Time to arrive	
emergency	ev_0_201.0	-1474	-612	(-1474', '1470', '-1002', '-854', '-831', '-612')	62.85881072099900	
emergency	ev_1_201.0	-338	-612	(-338', '-199', '68', '592', '-58', '60', '79', '-827', '-612')	106.70359577945400	
emergency	ev_2_201.0	-2182	-612	(-2182', '-1994', '-184', '-172', '164', '-162', '-75', '79', '-827', '-612')	115.44390061177100	
emergency	ev_3_201.0	-2251	-612	(-2251', '-2173', '-1980', '-1946', '-1785', '-1777', '-214', '-92', '79', '-827', '-612')	131.03007873692100	
emergency	ev_0_1101.0	-1474	-612	(-1474', '1470', '-1002', '-854', '-831', '-612')	62.85881072099900	

Figure 7: Snapshots of the current files containing the produced alerts, rerouted vehicles and emergency vehicle routes for scenario 5.

The safety-related KPIs that are calculated for each case, Time-To-Collision (TTC) and Deceleration Rate to Avoid Crash (DRAC), are defined as follows:

- TTC: Time-To-Collision:
If a following vehicle is approaching a lead vehicle with a relative speed:

$$TTC = \frac{d}{v_{rel}}$$

- d = distance between the vehicles
- $v_{rel} = v_{follower} - v_{leader}$
- TTC only applies if $v_{rel} > 0$

- DRAC: Deceleration Rate to Avoid Crash

$$DRAC = \frac{v_{rel}^2}{2d}$$

- d = distance between the vehicles
- $v_{rel} = v_{follower} - v_{leader}$

- DRAC only applies if $v_{rel} > 0$

Table 2: KPIs for two scenarios (4 and 5) with accident occurrence and the benchmark scenario (0, no incident, no rerouting). Tag 'ref' is the respective reference case where rerouting during incident is done only based on shortest path

Scenario	Total No Veh	Avg TT	Avg Delay	Avg waiting	Rerouted	Throughput	% TTC(H)	% DRAC(H)	Total CO2
scenario_000	6669	163.4	72.2	0.002	0	6435	5.03%	1.070%	5.580.E+09
scenario_004	6686	181.3	87.3	0.000	77	6482	5.39%	1.134%	6.055.E+09
scenario_004_ref	6685	187.4	93.7	0.049	0	6468	5.74%	1.112%	6.145.E+09
scenario_005	6686	255.9	157.1	0.181	207	6452	6.79%	1.095%	7.594.E+09
scenario_005_ref	6683	263.3	165.1	0.184	0	6393	6.83%	1.064%	7.758.E+09

Table 2 aggregates the calculated KPIs from two representative scenarios where an accident occurs which necessitates road closure. The table lists the following metrics: total number of departing trips, average travel time (sec/veh), average delay (sec/veh) which is defined as the additional time compared to free-flow conditions, the average wait time (sec/veh), the number of rerouted vehicles, the number of finished trips, the fraction of vehicles having TTC < 3 sec, the fraction of vehicles having DRAC > 3.4 sec, and the total produced volume of CO₂. We can see that compared to the reference cases, where no safety-optimized rerouting is done during the incident (just shortest distance), the average delay and travel time, as well as the values of TTC and DRAC reflecting safety are improved with the use of the route guidance tool implementing rerouting based on the safety-optimized cost function. Similar results are collected for most scenarios simulated so far. The analysis will continue for all types of incidents, where some calibration of the involved parameters may be necessary.

The implementation of the same framework to the traffic network of Graz (UC 1.1) is ongoing, with the building and calibration of the digital model of the city being prepared by UNI.EIFFEL. The completion of all necessary simulation tests and the development of the communication system to transmit the results to the iDriving platform is currently ongoing and is expected to be finished on time for the respective pilot.

4.3.2 Signal Control Tool (TUC)

The signal control tool is a traffic management system that makes dynamic adjustments to traffic light timings, by leveraging real-time data on traffic and queue formation, to improve performance in terms of traffic flow and travel time (delay), enhancing the efficiency and safety of urban traffic networks. The tool aims to help reduce phenomena of high congestion and gridlocks.

4.3.2.1 Concept and Design Phase

The main concept of a signal controller is to calculate varying traffic signal timings using information provided by detectors located at the approaches of a signalized junction. The design phase of the tool was preceded by an extensive review of the current literature and the State-of-the-Art approaches in traffic signal control, both for local as well as for network wide applications.

As already mentioned above, the integration framework for both of ITMS tools was decided after discussions between the main developing partners of the tools (MBL and TUC). The tools were conceived as modular components within the open-source traffic simulation software SUMO, enabling realistic simulation of traffic evolution in any network with available traffic data.

4.3.2.2 Methodological approach and technical framework

The approach followed utilizes the traffic light system already installed in SUMO (predefined phases and order) and changes the duration of each phase. The goal is to make sure that traffic lights change their timing based on the traffic conditions observed after application the route guidance decision and mimic in a way the real traffic lights installed in the related PUCs.

The signal control tool was developed using as a basis the well-known max-pressure (MP) algorithm (Varaiya, 2013). This is an algorithm that utilizes a minimum number of measurements to estimate the state of each link. We are using time occupancy measurements provided by loop detectors installed on each approaching link upstream of the traffic-light stop-line. These measurements are in fact used as a proxy for space occupancy on each link.

Development has been conducted using SUMO's TraCI API, implemented in C++, ensuring modularity, interoperability, and compatibility with future platform extensions. The signal control tool was integrated into SUMO and related testing was performed.

4.3.2.3 Use Case configuration, Implementation and Outcomes

Given the lack of available digital models and real traffic data for the project's PUCs during the first phase of iDriving, the initial development and testing of the tool was done on a synthetic network with a single junction that was created using SUMO functions, as shown in Figure 8. Building the setup of this synthetic network prior to working on the specific use case cities involved in the project allowed for a fast kick-off of the initial development, debugging, validation and functionality testing of the signal control tool under controlled conditions. It also allowed for documenting all the requirements for constructing the SUMO model and simulation setup for the upcoming PUCs, such as the need for traffic signal settings (phase sequence, nominal duration, etc.).

A one-hour long artificial travel demand scenario with a single vehicle type (cars) was produced to simulate realistic traffic dynamics and enable early functional

validation of the tool. Traffic signal timings were assigned for two stages of the signal plan, also shown in Figure 8. The first stage serves the north and the south single-lane links, while the second stage serves the west and east single-lane links. All approaches (links) allow for three different movements at the traffic signal: straight, left and right.

Figure 8: Snapshot of the synthetic network with a single junction in SUMO. The signal plan used in the no-control case

A first set of simulations was performed for 10 different seeds, i.e. 10 repetitions using a nominal signal plan with constant signal timing, i.e. no control is applied. 40 seconds of green time were assigned per stage followed by 3 seconds of yellow time and 2 seconds of all-red time. The aforementioned timing produces a signal cycle of 90 seconds. The demand scenario is such that strong congestion is created on the north and south links during the first half of the simulation period followed by strong congestion on the west and east links during the second half. This is shown, for one of the replications, in Figure 9. The high occupancy measurements (averages over each cycle) observed represent congested situations with long queues spilling back on the corresponding links.

Figure 9: Occupancy measurements per link and green duration for the two stages in the no-control case

The yellow and all-red times mentioned above lead to a lost time, i.e. a time period that cannot be shared between different approaches, which has a duration of 10 seconds. Assuming that each stage needs to have a minimum green time of 10 seconds, we end up with 60 seconds that can be shared between the two stages based on the decisions of the MP algorithm. Figure 10 presents a snapshot from the simulation when control is applied using the MP algorithm. The signal plan produced in the control case is also shown for the last two cycles completed at the time of the snapshot. We can observe that the timings are not constant anymore. For the replication discussed above, the occupancy measurements per link as well as the green duration for the two stages is shown for the control case in Figure 11. The high occupancy measurements (averages over each cycle) observed previously are obviously reduced because the controlled green durations allow for the best usage of the available time within a cycle, without falling below the minimum green requirements.

Figure 10: Snapshot of the synthetic network with a single junction in SUMO. The signal plan produced in the control case is also shown for 2 cycles

Figure 11: Occupancy measurements per link and green duration for the two stages in the control case

The produced results were evaluated through a defined set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), to assess the effectiveness of the proposed traffic light timings. KPIs include the improvement in Total Travel Time (TTS), Total Delay (TD) and average speed. The comparison of the control case is done with the reference no-control case and is presented in Table 3. It can be observed that a 77% increase is achieved on the average speed of the vehicles when control is applied, while TD is improved by 99% and TTS is improved by 42%. These results are an excellent indication for use of the algorithm at a local level on each one of the major signalized junctions of the simulated PUCs.

Table 3: KPIs used to assess the effectiveness of the proposed traffic light timings

Replications	No Control			Control		
	TTS (veh-sec)	TD (veh-sec)	Av. Speed (m/s)	TTS (veh-sec)	TD (veh-sec)	Av. Speed (m/s)
1	290909	150736	6.20	167338	1858	11.03
2	298441	185008	6.13	173971	2558	10.87
3	304916	223920	6.11	175967	2331	11.15
4	296125	205890	6.26	171286	2141	11.19
5	294378	171776	6.23	172689	2137	10.89
6	306365	239624	5.98	177674	3200	11.02
7	295930	190784	6.27	178517	1983	10.75
8	296675	189550	6.32	171322	1906	11.16
9	284757	135215	6.41	168487	1925	11.02
10	281089	140851	6.35	165303	1930	11.21
Averages	294958	183335	6.23	172255	2197	11.03

4.4 Next steps

The upcoming activities related to the route guidance tool can be summarized in the following points:

- Completion of calibration of demand for the Graz UC.
- Generation of the described in D2.2 incident scenarios associated with Graz use case (increased traffic occurrence) in all the critical points of the network with the creation of the respective alert files.
- Deployment of the route guidance tool in SUMO simulation runs and storing of the generated results in the previously described format (same as in the synthetic network).

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- Evaluation of the generated results by calculating the predefined KPIs.
 - Ensuring the retrieval of the correct stored results for the respective incident scenario in the real-time deployment of the iDriving platform.
- Signal Control Tool

The upcoming activities related to the signal control tool include its deployment in SUMO simulation runs for the Graz PUC. This will allow for simulation runs for the route guidance tool.

5 Mobile and in-vehicle applications for early warnings

5.1 Description

Task 3.3 focuses on developing user-centric mobile and in-vehicle applications that deliver real-time safety warnings and guidance to a wide range of road users. These applications – either embedded in a vehicle’s infotainment system or used through a standalone mobile app – connect directly to vehicle sensors and the project’s Digital Twin environments to retrieve up-to-date information on road conditions, traffic states, incidents, and other potential hazards. The system presents these alerts in a clear and non-distracting manner, offering actionable advice such as speed adjustments, alternative route suggestions, or notifications of dangerous conditions. Importantly, the mobile app extends these capabilities to cyclists, pedestrians, and other non-driving users, ensuring that the safety benefits reach all modes of transport. The task also enables two-way communication, allowing users to report unexpected road conditions, which are then fed back into the broader system to enhance accuracy and responsiveness. Overall, Task 3.3 provides the human-facing layer of the iDriving ecosystem, supporting safer and more informed mobility through timely and context-aware safety information.

5.2 Objectives

Task 3.3 focuses on a set of clear objectives that guide the development of the mobile application. First, it aims to design the application’s functionality and user interface so that they fully meet the defined requirements and overall project goals. A second objective is to ensure high standards of usability, accessibility, and interface quality, making these elements central to the development approach. Additionally, the task sets out to deliver an Android-based application capable of operating globally, in alignment with the overarching architecture. Finally, Task 3.3 includes the objective to carry out multiple testing phases, allowing the team to assess the application’s behaviour and performance across a range of conditions and scenarios.

5.3 Current progress

To date, focus has primarily been set to the implementation of mobile and in-vehicle applications for early warnings.

The partners involved in this task collaborated with the rest of the Consortium for identifying the user requirements applicable to each use case of the project. Once outlined, the user requirements were further discussed and later consolidated within the deliverable D2.2 – User, Safety and Ethic Requirements & Pilot Use Cases

Handbook. As the partners progressed with the activities, they established as well the technical requirements for the mobile and in-vehicle applications. These requirements, together with the architecture aspects for all the components targeted for implementation within the project, were described in deliverable D2.3 – Technical Requirements and Digital Ecosystem Architecture.

The identified user and technical requirements were a basis for the development of the mobile and in-vehicle applications. Starting from these elements, a set of mock-ups was created for the mobile and in-vehicle application. The mock-ups were reviewed with the Consortium members and updated as necessary according to the partners’ feedback or to the aspects identified throughout the development process, so that the objectives and requirements are fulfilled.

Some examples for the mobile application mock-ups developed can be seen in Figure 12, while examples for the in-vehicle application mock-ups can be seen in Figure 13.

Figure 12: Mobile application mock-ups example

Figure 13: In-vehicle application mock-ups example

Within T3.3 the partners defined the technical elements of the mobile and in-vehicle application and the involved workflows and documented them in deliverable D5.1 First iDriving Prototype Based on the user and technical requirements previously defined, the implementation for the mobile and in-vehicle applications started, with the components involved in these applications being developed in parallel and ultimately being foreseen for integration to obtain the end-result. Along the implementation, the partners organized periodic technical meetings for aligning on all the related elements and for ensuring the communication between components.

Tests on the connection were performed, using the Kafka server, both remotely and in-person during UC rehearsals. The data collected during the test have been further used in the adjustments of the applications.

In addition, a methodology for real-time identification and systematic collection of appropriate KPIs to effectively inform safety assessments and decision-making processes has been developed, and currently being implemented and validated through extensive simulation, based on real use cases by adoption a cross-platform integration (SUMO and CARLA). The methodology would further suggest improvements for in-vehicle applications for early warnings.

5.4 Next steps

In the upcoming period, the development of the mobile and in-vehicle applications will continue in collaboration with all involved partners, with tests also to be continued throughout the implementation process. In addition, continuous adjustments brought to the GUI and functionalities will be implemented, based on feedback and suggestions from partners, and testing results.

A first version of the mobile and in-vehicle is targeted to be available in the first part of 2026, before the pilot in UC 1.1 Graz, Austria.

6 Aerial Surveillance in Incident Management and Maintenance Tasks

6.1 Description

This part of the project focuses on the development and integration of an aerial drone-based surveillance solution to support incident management and infrastructure maintenance within the iDriving ecosystem. It aims to enhance situational awareness and data collection capabilities across both urban and rural road networks, complementing the ground-based sensors and vehicle systems developed in other tasks.

The Unmanned Aerial System (UAS) that is designed, deployed and tested, is equipped with an RGB sensor to enable near-real-time monitoring of critical events such as traffic incidents. The aerial data will be transmitted to the iDriving system to facilitate rapid assessment and decision-making.

Emphasis will be placed on the integration of an onboard processor for AI-assisted detection algorithms, enabling faster and more autonomous incident recognition. Pilot activities will demonstrate the value of aerial surveillance in various scenarios, including incident assessment and traffic management optimization.

6.2 Objectives

This part of the project is structured around a set of specific objectives that guide the development and integration of UAV capabilities within the iDriving framework. The first objective is to develop an aerial surveillance tool designed specifically for iDriving's road safety and maintenance needs. A second objective is to integrate and validate drone-based sensing technologies capable of detecting incidents and infrastructure damage, such as road surface defects. The task also aims to establish robust communication links and data exchange protocols, ensuring that aerial data can interact seamlessly with the broader iDriving ecosystem. Another key objective is to demonstrate operational scenarios for UAV-assisted incident response and maintenance planning, evaluating their efficiency and reliability in real-world conditions. In addition, the task seeks to ensure full compliance with EU drone regulations and safety standards, providing clear guidelines for UAV operations in public and semi-urban environments. Finally, it includes the objective to support maintenance activities through high-resolution aerial datasets, enabling detailed infrastructure condition assessment and improved risk mapping.

6.3 Current progress

6.3.1 Approach

The MANTIS is a high-performance quad-rotor UAV developed to support aerial surveillance within the iDriving project. It features a powerful NVIDIA onboard processor that enables near real-time data processing and the execution of advanced AI-based algorithms directly during flight. The platform supports autonomous waypoint missions through QGroundControl, allowing for flexible and precise flight operations. It also offers automated take-off and landing capabilities for enhanced operational safety and reliability.

The iDriving UAV will be equipped with an RGB camera, gimbal, PX4 flight controller, and an embedded GPU for efficient edge processing. With a take-off weight of 2.4 kg and a flight time of approximately at least 25 minutes in hovering conditions, MANTIS provides an optimal balance between endurance, manoeuvrability, and computational power for incident monitoring and infrastructure inspection tasks.

Trials and test flights will be conducted for system validation, during which incremental adjustments and fine-tuning will be made to minimize potential component errors and optimize performance.

Figure 14: Images of the NVIDIA processor and the SIYI A8 mini

The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the technology offered has progressed from level 4 to level 5. Upon completion of the program and implementation of the required advancements to meet the needs of the project, it is projected to reach level 6, marking a significant step towards operational deployment and widespread use.

6.3.2 Preliminary results

The hardware design of the iDriving UAV represents the outcome of a systematic development process focused on achieving a reliable aerial platform capable of supporting advanced surveillance operations. The design integrates all essential components including propulsion, control, sensing, and processing units into a compact and efficient configuration optimized for both performance and

endurance. Particular attention was given to stability, vibration damping, and power distribution, ensuring consistent performance during autonomous missions. The resulting UAV design provides a robust foundation for real-time data acquisition and edge processing.

6.3.2.1 Hardware Design

- CAD Design and Process Analysis

The 3D design of this drone has been conducted using DS SOLIDWORKS CAD software. The mechanical/structural design follows the steps below:

- Estimation Design
 1. Definition of all the electronic equipment that shall be installed on the drone (pilot, power distribution system, GPS antenna, telemetry, onboard processor, camera etc.).
 2. Material definition for the construction of the frame, arms and landing gear: The essence of the structural design of flying systems is to achieve the minimum possible overall weight (to minimize the power demands for the flight and extend the flight duration and capabilities) while maintaining sufficient structural stiffness to satisfy the design requirements. A parameter of outmost importance that contributes to this is the structural materials. Thus, the main material selected for the construction is carbon fibre-epoxy composite. This material has a very low density (around 1.6 kg of mass per litre of volume) with excellent mechanical properties and is available in sheets of various thicknesses and tubes of various diameters. Structural components that are too complex to be constructed with the above-mentioned carbon fibre elements, are 3D printed with suitable materials (e.g., carbon fibre filament) and stainless-steel bolted connections are used where it is necessary. Finally, commercially available aluminium components are used in some cases (e.g., tube clamps and spacers).
 3. Given the above, a rough layout is sketched, to determine the overall geometry/ dimensions and the total weight of the drone.
 4. With these parameters defined, the number of rotors of the multicopter and the size-model of motors/ propellers, electronic speed controllers and battery - power management system size can be determined.
 5. The equipment defined on step 4 may affect the previous weight – size & layout estimations (made on step 3), so steps 3 - 4 may be repeated until the final data output of step 4 converges with these of step 3.
- Detail Design

The above estimation process is followed by the detailed design. At this stage all the equipment is determined. Correctly dimensioned 3D models of the components – complete with their mass properties, are imported in the CAD

software. Their position on the drone is determined, taking care to satisfy the following requirements:

- Ensure that every component is properly installed on the frame, in such a manner that does not obstruct its function or the function of the adjacent components.
- Ensure that the components that shall need frequent inspection and/ or hand -operation are easily accessible.
- Minimize the distances between equipment that shall be connected (with cable).
- Ensure that the total centre of gravity is kept close to the geometric centre of the drone.

Frame

The UAV frame consists primarily of two flat carbon fibre sheets and four arm mounts, which also act as structural elements. Slots and holes were incorporated into the frame to facilitate the installation of components and cable routing while maintaining structural integrity.

Figure 15: 3D designed UAV frame

Arms with Motors and Propellers

The UAV arms feature a foldable joint mechanism that allows for easier transport and compact storage when the drone is not in use. This design significantly reduces the overall footprint during transportation while maintaining rigidity during flight.

Figure 16. Arm with Motor - Propeller pair

The landing gear is integrated into the arms and designed to provide a stable and impact-resistant base for the UAV during take-off and landing operations.

Figure 17. Assembled landing gear in the drone's arms

Camera Assembly

The camera, gimbal, and damping plate are supplied as a complete unit by SIYI Company. The assembly is suspended beneath one of the carbon fibre plates that make up the drone's frame, ensuring effective vibration isolation and stable image acquisition during flight.

Figure 18. Flir Camera c/w gimbal and damping plate installed below the drone

Completed Drone Assembly

After completing the sub-assemblies, all electronic components, power cables, and signal wiring were installed in their designated positions according to the final CAD design. The result is a fully integrated UAV that meets the design requirements for compactness, balance, and modularity.

Figure 19. iDriving UAV - Total Assembly

6.3.2.2 Technical specifications

- iDriving UAV Technical Specifications

In this paragraph, we are presenting a matrix that includes the main technical specifications for the UAV.

Table 4: iDriving UAV Technical Specifications

Parameter	Value
Dimensions	690 x 690 mm
Weight	2.3 kg
Battery capacity	4 Ah
Flight time w/ Typical Payload	25-30 min
Available payload weight	300gr

- System Requirements

This section outlines the main system requirements for the iDriving UAV and the necessary ground equipment to ensure reliable operation, maintenance, and validation of the aerial system.

Table 5. iDriving UAV System Requirements

Requirements	Description
Battery voltage: 22.2V	1 x 6S LiPo battery.
Battery charger.	Battery charger that can charge 2 LiPo batteries simultaneously (up to 6S).
Radio transmitter for manual piloting.	Radio transmitter, compatible with the embedded autopilot, suitable for manual piloting and monitoring of the power consumption.
Laptop with the QGroundControl software installed.	This is necessary for maintenance and flight purposes.

6.3.3 Requirements for successful pilot validation

To ensure the successful validation of the iDriving UAV during pilot activities, all relevant infrastructural, environmental, spatial, and regulatory requirements must be met. Addressing these aspects comprehensively will enable a safe, compliant, and effective execution of the pilot demonstrations.

Infrastructure

- Availability of adequate space for UAV take-off and landing.
- Secure storage facilities for UAVs and associated equipment.
- Access to power sources for charging batteries and operating auxiliary systems.
- Reliable communication networks to support real-time telemetry and data transmission.

Environmental

- Favourable weather conditions suitable for safe flight operations.
- Minimal interference from wind, precipitation, or dust to ensure stability and data quality.
- Adherence to environmental regulations and restrictions applicable to the operational area.

Spatial

- Sufficient airspace clearance and absence of restricted or no-fly zones within the operational environment.
- Clear line of sight (LOS) between the UAV and the ground control station to maintain stable communication.

Regulatory Compliance

- Acquisition of all flight clearances and authorizations from the relevant local aviation authorities prior to testing.
- Full compliance with local, national, and international UAV regulations, ensuring lawful and safe operation within the designated airspace.

By systematically fulfilling these requirements, the iDriving UAV will be validated under realistic conditions, supporting its integration into the project's broader framework for incident management and infrastructure maintenance.

6.4 Next steps

The upcoming phase will focus on manufacturing, refining, and validating the UAV system to ensure optimal performance in the next pilot demonstrations. Feedback collected from the rehearsal in Nevers will be incorporated to improve the UAV's deployment procedures and operational reliability.

All required algorithms will be implemented on the onboard NVIDIA processor to enable autonomous data processing and AI-assisted detection during upcoming tests. A series of laboratory and field experiments will be carried out in close collaboration with project partners to validate system performance, safety, and responsiveness under real-world conditions.

Additionally, the operational scenarios that the iDriving UAV will execute during the final demonstrations will be clearly defined, ensuring alignment with the project's overall objectives. Continuous coordination with the pilot leaders will also ensure that all necessary flight authorizations are obtained on time, guaranteeing smooth, compliant, and safe UAV operations throughout the pilot phase.

7 Dynamic Resource Allocation for Optimized Safety Surveillance

7.1 Description

This part of the project focuses on the development of an autonomous UAV mission planning system capable of generating efficient coverage paths for monitoring and inspection missions. The task addresses both single-UAV and multi-UAV scenarios, enabling unmanned aerial vehicles to scan a defined Area of Interest while respecting operational constraints such as no-fly zones and vehicle-specific limitations. The work carried out includes the specification of requirements, the design and implementation of the planning algorithms, their integration into the broader iDriving system, and the execution of tests to validate functionality. Early explorations considered multiple planning modes, but the scope was refined to concentrate exclusively on systematic coverage of a continuous area, reflecting real operational needs. As a result, this task delivers a unified coverage path planning module designed to support real-time, reliable, and efficient UAV mission execution within the iDriving platform.

7.2 Objectives

The objective of this task is to develop a UAV-based mission planning service capable of autonomously generating complete and efficient coverage paths for a specified mission area. The task aims to ensure that the system can allocate one or more UAVs to an area based on its size and the number of available platforms, while also selecting flight paths that align with the capabilities and constraints of each drone. By doing so, the task seeks to maximise area coverage, improve operational efficiency, and support real-time inspection or incident-response missions through an integrated, AI-driven planning solution.

7.3 Current progress

7.3.1 Requirements Specification

A thorough requirements analysis was conducted at project outset to guide the development. These requirements were documented in Deliverable D2.3, capturing both functional capabilities and interoperability needs. The key technical requirements defined include:

- TR-FUN-3.5-1: Mission Area Definition. The system shall allow the user to define a mission area as input. This implies providing an interface to specify the region of interest (ROI) – for example, by drawing a polygon on a map in WGS84 coordinates. The mission area definition may include boundaries of the area to cover, and optionally internal obstacles or no-fly zones within that

area. This requirement ensures the planner knows *where* the UAVs must operate.

- TR-FUN-3.5-2: Single-UAV Coverage Path Planning. The system shall be able to compute a complete coverage path for a single UAV given the mission area. In other words, using one drone, it must generate a path that covers the entire specified region without gaps. The path should be efficient (minimize redundant coverage and flight time) while adhering to vehicle constraints (e.g. turning radius, battery endurance) and avoiding any no-fly zones.
- TR-FUN-3.5-3: Multi-UAV Cooperative Path Planning. The system shall extend the coverage planner to support multiple UAVs working cooperatively. When more than one UAV is available for a mission, the planner should divide the work among them – partitioning the area or the task in a sensible way – and produce coordinated routes for each UAV. The objective is to maximize parallel coverage and reduce mission completion time, without overlap or collision between UAVs. This involves deciding how to allocate portions of the area to each drone and planning their individual coverage paths accordingly.
- TR-NFUN-3.5-1: Data Interoperability and Format. All inputs and outputs of the Task 3.5 planning component shall adhere to a standardized data schema for interoperability. In practice, this means the mission input (area boundaries, UAV parameters, etc.) and the resulting flight plans are formatted in a well-defined JSON structure. By using a common schema, the path planner can integrate seamlessly with other components of the iDriving system (such as user interfaces and the mission execution module). This non-functional requirement ensures consistent communication and easy integration of the planner via messaging or APIs.

These requirements were derived from user needs and overall system objectives. They set a clear target for development: the system must allow users to input a polygonal area, then output one or more UAV routes that fully cover that area. It is important to note that Coverage Path Planning (CPP) is the fundamental problem being solved – it is defined as determining a path for a vehicle such that the entire region of interest is covered. The CPP problem is known to be NP-hard in general, meaning optimal solutions are computationally complex; therefore, the system is expected to use efficient heuristic methods to produce good coverage paths in a reasonable time.

7.3.2 System Architecture and Integration Design

To meet the above requirements, the Task 3.5 solution was designed as a modular component within the iDriving platform. The data flow for the UAV mission planning system is as follows:

- **Input Layer:** The primary inputs to the planner are the Mission Specification (including the area polygon and any no-fly zones) and UAV Parameters (such as number of UAVs, each UAV's flight speed and altitude). These inputs will be provided by the user through a front-end interface (interactive map and forms).
- **Processing Layer (Path Planning Engine):** The core of the component is the coverage path planning engine. This engine ingests the mission input and computes the flight paths. It is implemented as a software module (service) that can run independently and communicate via messages. The planning engine comprises algorithms for area coverage (detailed in the next section) and logic to handle both single-UAV and multi-UAV cases. Internally, the engine may perform steps like:
 1. Preprocessing the input polygon (e.g., simplifying geometry or splitting if needed).
 2. Incorporating no-fly zones by treating them as obstacles within the area.
 3. Computing a coverage route (or multiple routes for multiple drones) through systematic sweep patterns.
 4. Packaging the resulting path(s) into the required JSON output format.
- **Output Layer:** The output of the planner is a Mission Plan, which includes one or more flight paths. Each path is essentially a sequence of GPS waypoints (latitude, longitude, altitude) that the UAV should follow to cover the area. Additional data may include the ordering of waypoints, estimated distances or times, and identifiers if multiple UAVs are involved. The output is produced as a JSON message (satisfying the schema) and delivered to the mission execution component (T3.4) that will dispatch commands to the UAVs.
- **Integration via Kafka Broker:** A critical design choice was to use Apache Kafka as the message broker to connect the planning engine with other parts of the system. Kafka provides a distributed publish/subscribe messaging infrastructure that achieves high-throughput, low-latency data exchange. In our architecture, the planning service subscribes to a dedicated "iDriving_path_planning" topic on the Kafka bus. When a user defines a mission and submits it. The planning engine, upon consuming the message, performs the computation and then publishes the resulting plan JSON to a "iDriving_path_planning" topic. Consumers i.e. the UAV control system subscribes to the output topic. This event-driven integration ensures loose coupling between components and real-time data flow across the platform.

The above architecture was implemented and refined over M3-M18. The use of Kafka proved valuable in system-wide integration, as it allowed the Task 3.5 module to be developed and tested in isolation and then seamlessly plugged

into the larger iDriving ecosystem. Other modules can interface with the planner simply by producing or consuming the relevant Kafka topics, without direct hard-coded connections. This design greatly improves flexibility and interoperability, fulfilling the TR-NFUN-3.5-1 requirement in practice.

7.3.3 Coverage Path Planning Algorithm Implementation

The heart of Task 3.5 is the coverage path planning algorithm. This section details how the system computes coverage paths for both single and multiple UAVs, including the strategies and logic used.

7.3.3.1 Single-UAV Coverage Path Planning

For a single UAV mission, the planning algorithm must generate a continuous path that covers the entire target area. The approach adopted can be described as a “lawnmower” sweep or boustrophedon pattern, which is a common strategy for complete coverage. In essence, the algorithm fills the area with parallel flight lines that the UAV will follow back-and-forth (hence the term *lawnmower*, akin to mowing a lawn in stripes).

Algorithm Outline:

1. Area Preprocessing:

For the purpose of covering a continuous area, it is essential to deploy a method that provides safe and efficient paths while ensuring complete coverage of the agricultural field. To efficiently cope with challenges faced in real-world scenarios, one should analyse all the aspects that govern Coverage Path Planning (CPP) problems (Galceran & Carreras, 2013). With the term CPP, we refer to the task of determining a path that passes through all the points of an area while avoiding any No-Fly Zones (NFZs)/Obstacles possible defined within the operational area.

In T3.5, the proposed platform deals with the problem of designing a path given:

A. Field-based information

- A *user-defined polygon* (A) that contains a series of points defining the Area of Interest to be scanned.
- A *user-defined sub-polygon* (\emptyset), if needed, representing any no-fly zones (NFZs) or obstacles within A .

B. UAV-based information

- The *scanning density* (in meters), representing the distance between two adjacent flight-path lines.
- The *flight direction* (in degrees), defining the direction of the path within A .
- The *flight altitude* of the UAV for the mission.
- The *speed* of the UAV for the mission.

The objective is to compile all this user-defined information and extract a set of coordinates, representing a safe and efficient path, to provide a complete coverage of the \$A\$. Note that the defined problem does not assume any type of UAV but rather adapts to each UAV's capabilities by tuning the UAV-based info (as defined previously) accordingly.

7.3.3.2 Field Approximation on Grid

Assume that the field to be covered has an arbitrary shape and is represented as a two-dimensional polygon A , defined by a set of coordinate points (x, y) . The first step is to represent A as a grid. To approximate the polygon on a grid, A is divided into a finite number of equal, non-overlapping cells that together fill the entire area of the field. The number of these cells corresponds to the spatial resolution required for UAV-based imaging used to monitor crop growth. In the proposed platform, the spatial resolution is determined by the *flight altitude* and the *scanning density*.

The grid representation of A is defined as the set:

$$U = \{ (x, y) : x \text{ ranges from } 1 \text{ to } rows, \text{ and } y \text{ ranges from } 1 \text{ to } cols \}$$

Here, *rows* and *cols* are the number of rows and columns resulting from the discretization of the field. Thus, the total number of grid cells is:

$$n = rows \times cols$$

During the grid decomposition, we assume that there are n_o obstacles, each occupying the size of a single cell and located at known positions. The set of these obstacle cells is:

$$O = \{ (x, y) \text{ in } U : (x, y) \text{ is occupied} \}$$

Each obstacle corresponds to a cell that represents an obstructed portion of the real field. Consequently, the number of cells that need to be covered is reduced to:

$$l = n - n_o$$

The set of unoccupied cells that should be covered is:

$$L = U \setminus O \text{ (that is, all grid cells except those marked as obstacles)}$$

7.3.3.3 Nodes Placement

After defining the operational area U , we specify the allowable UAV movements from each grid cell within L so that the agricultural field A can be fully covered. To do this, we introduce an undirected weighted graph $G = (V, E)$. Each vertex in G corresponds to the centre of a grid cell in the set L and is represented as a node. Edges between these nodes represent the allowed UAV movements within L . In general, each node connects to the four adjacent nodes following the Von Neumann neighbourhood. Nodes located on the boundaries of the operational area or next to obstacles have fewer connections.

1. Navigation Algorithm:

Having illustrated all the prime features that constitute a completely safe and efficient path, we proceed to present a navigation algorithm in steps, as sketched in Figure 20 for solving the problem. The navigation system that we have developed, utilizes the Spanning Tree Algorithm (Dong et al., 2020) which deploys a coverage path planning algorithm as the UAV covers any arbitrary shape, while knowing in advance any related information about the location of the NFZs/Obstacles. Conceptually, this algorithm tackles the aforementioned challenges and achieves the overall mission objectives within six distinct steps.

Figure 20: Spanning-Tree Coverage algorithm main steps. Subfigure (a – top left) illustrates the initial grid discretization and the position of the obstacles. Subfigures (b – top middle, and c – top right) illustrate the allowed UAV movements within the grid and schematically outlines the mathematical symbols. Subfigure (d – bottom left) illustrates the Minimum Spanning Tree among the allowed movements. Subfigure (e – bottom middle) depicts the Minimum Spanning Tree to the original discrete area. Subfigure (f – bottom right) illustrates the path that circumnavigates the Minimum Spanning Tree and the final path that covers the original terrain.

1. Output Path:

The final output for a single-UAV case is an ordered list of waypoints forming a loop or route that starts and ends at designated points (for example, the start could be a specified take-off location or an edge of the area). The path guarantees complete coverage of the mission area – meaning the UAV's sensor will have passed over every point in the area at least once. *Complete coverage planning* ensures no gaps remain in the surveyed region. The nature of the coverage path planning problem

and this solution approach mean that while the path is not mathematically optimal (due to the NP-hardness of CPP), it is a practical heuristic that yields near-optimal results in reasonable computation time.

7.3.3.4 Multi-UAV Cooperative Path Planning

When multiple UAVs are available for the mission, the planning problem becomes more complex but also more efficient in potential outcome. The objective for multi-UAV planning is to divide the coverage task among the drones so that they work in parallel and finish the job faster than a single UAV could. Our development for multi-UAV cooperative planning built upon the single-UAV algorithm, extending it to coordinate multiple paths.

Strategy: The basic strategy implemented is area partitioning with independent coverage. The mission area is divided into sub-regions, and each UAV is assigned a sub-region to cover. This is a common approach in multi-UAV coverage planning – by segmenting the area into several parts equal to the number of UAVs, and giving each UAV its own region, the coverage problem can be reduced to multiple independent single-UAV problems. All UAVs can then operate concurrently in their respective regions without interfering with each other. The key challenge is how to partition the area optimally. In our approach, the partitioning aims to balance the workload among UAVs (each sub-region should ideally take around the same time to cover) and minimize any idle time or excessive travel between sub-regions.

Partitioning Method: For the partitioning method we utilized the DARP (Kapoutsis et al., 2017) algorithm. The DARP (Divide Areas Algorithm for Optimal Multi-Robot Coverage Path Planning) method proposes a systematic way to partition a workspace so that multiple robots can cover it efficiently and without overlap.

In the DARP framework, the environment is first discretized into grid cells. Then, using an iterative partitioning procedure, the algorithm allocates to each robot a contiguous, compact, and balanced region. The balancing ensures that each robot receives approximately the same number of cells, while contiguity ensures the region is obstacle-free and fully reachable, as shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21: Area allocation during different time-steps of DARP execution

The key idea is that DARP treats the assignment as an optimization problem: it adjusts the partition boundaries until every robot's region is connected and the overall workload is balanced. Once the partitions are finalized, each robot generates its own coverage path inside its assigned region, leading to efficient multi-robot coordination with minimal redundancy or interference.

Multi-UAV Path Planning: Once the area is partitioned, the planner generates a coverage path per UAV. This is essentially running the single-UAV path planning algorithm on each sub-region independently.

Output for Multi-UAV: The output JSON in the multi-UAV case contains separate waypoint lists for each UAV, along with an identifier for which UAV should take which path. Each path covers one sub-region fully. The result is that the entire area is covered when considering all UAVs' paths collectively, with no overlap between the paths. The system is effectively performing cooperative coverage path planning, and the approach aligns with known methods where multiple UAVs maximize coverage by dividing the area.

Overall, the also implemented multi-UAV planning meets the requirement TR-FUN-3.5-3 by allowing cooperative missions.

7.3.4 Frontend Interface Development

In parallel with the backend algorithm development, an initial frontend interface was designed and implemented to enable user interaction with the UAV mission planning system. This frontend serves as both a demonstration of Task 3.5 capabilities and a practical tool for mission configuration. The development prioritized an intuitive user experience and real-time visualization of planning results. Key features of the front-end include:

- **Mission Area Input via Interactive Map:** The interface features an interactive map (using a mapping library with satellite or street layer) where users can draw the mission area polygon. Users can click to place vertices and outline the region of interest on the map. The coordinates (latitude/longitude) of the polygon's vertices are captured in WGS84 format. This visual method makes it easy to precisely define complex boundaries. The map interface also allows marking no-fly zones or obstacles as smaller polygons within the main area, if needed, so that they can be accounted for in planning.
- **UAV Parameter Input Forms:** A set of form fields is provided for the user to enter mission parameters. This includes the number of UAVs to deploy, and specifications for each UAV such as flight altitude, cruise speed, and estimated flight time or battery capacity. The form also may include inputs for sensor footprint (or desired coverage resolution) which influences path spacing. By adjusting these parameters, the user can simulate different scenarios (e.g., two slow drones vs. one fast drone) and the planner will adapt accordingly. The form uses validation to ensure entries are within plausible ranges (for example, altitude must be positive, number of UAVs must be at least 1, etc.).
- **Real-Time Preview of Flight Paths:** Once the user defines the area and parameters, they can request the planner to generate a solution. The frontend is integrated with the backend such that it sends the input data (as JSON) and then listens for the planner's output. Upon receiving the planned routes, the interface plots the flight path(s) on the map in real-time. Different coloured lines can represent different UAVs' paths when multiple drones are used. This visual feedback lets the user immediately see the coverage pattern – the back-and-forth sweep lines covering the polygon, and any avoidance of no-fly zones visible. It effectively provides a preview of what the UAVs will fly. Users can zoom or pan the map to inspect the route details. If the plan is unsatisfactory (for instance, the user might see too many turns or some area uncovered due to an input mistake), they can adjust inputs and re-plan.
- **JSON Input/Output Handling:** Under the hood, the frontend is built to send and receive data in the standardized JSON format defined for Task 3.5. When the user draws the polygon and fills the form, the data is serialized to JSON

matching the schema (TR-NFUN-3.5-1) and sent to the backend (either via a REST API call that then publishes to Kafka, or directly via a WebSocket/event that ties into Kafka – depending on integration mode). Likewise, the response containing the flight path(s) is expected as JSON and is parsed by the frontend. This design ensures that the frontend and backend are loosely coupled; the UI does not need to know the internal details of the algorithm, only the input/output contract. It also means the planner could be swapped out or updated without changing the frontend, as long as the JSON contract remains the same.

- **Responsive and Modular Design:** The interface is implemented as a web-based application (compatible with modern browsers). It uses a responsive layout so that it can be accessed on various screen sizes (desktop, tablet). The mapping component and form components are built as modular units, anticipating future enhancements. For example, the map drawing tool is modular enough that new shapes (like corridors or points) could be allowed in the future, and the parameter form can easily be extended with new fields (like UAV model selection or advanced settings). The code structure separates data handling from presentation, which has made maintenance easier as the backend messages evolved. The result is a flexible UI that can grow with the project's needs.

The frontend development was iterative; early versions were tested by team members to gather feedback on usability. Through those tests, we are in the process of refining features like the polygon drawing (adding the ability to edit points) and improving the clarity of the displayed paths (e.g., using markers or arrows to indicate start and end of the path, numbering waypoints, etc.). T3.5 will integrate the front-end with the planner back-end until the next version of D3. An early illustrating example of the path planning UI can be shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22: Path Planning User Interface

7.3.5 Testing and Validation

Testing has been a crucial part of Task 3.5’s development to ensure the reliability and accuracy of the mission planning system. A combination of integration tests, and simulation-based validation was employed to verify that each component works correctly on its own and within the larger system.

- **Simulation Testing:** To validate that the planned UAV paths are feasible in practice, we utilized simulation-based testing. Using a UAV simulator environment (Shah et al., 2018), we imported the flight paths generated by the planner to see how virtual drones would execute them (Figure 23). During the simulations, the UAV successfully followed the waypoints, and we visually confirmed that the camera footprint covered the entire target area in the simulation. We tested multi-UAV plans in simulation as well: 3, 7, 11, 15 and 19 drones were sent along their respective paths simultaneously. The simulation allowed us to verify there were no intersections or unsafe proximities between drones. It also helped measure coverage efficiency – e.g., estimated flight time and percentage of coverage.

Figure 23. Several Scenarios were tested through the UAV Simulator

- Integration Testing: Integration tests were then carried out to ensure that the Task 3.5 module works when connected to other parts of the iDriving system. This included testing the end-to-end data flow: from the frontend interface through Kafka to the back-end planner. One scenario tested was a full mission creation in the UI – drawing an area, inputting parameters, clicking “Plan” – and then checking that a plan appears on the UI map within a reasonable time. This end-to-end test validated the JSON formatting on both ends (T3.5 -> T3.4) and the messaging via Kafka. These integration tests confirm that the Task 3.5 planner can be reliably integrated in the iDriving system. More integrations test will be held during the next period.

7.4 Next steps

The work completed so far establishes a solid foundation for the UAV mission planning system, demonstrating reliable coverage path generation, multi-UAV coordination, and successful integration with the iDriving architecture. The next phase of development will focus on refining system performance, enhancing usability, and preparing the module for full validation within project demonstrations.

In the coming period, the planning algorithm will be further optimized to improve coverage efficiency, waypoint smoothness, obstacle handling, and workload distribution across multiple UAVs. These enhancements will target reductions in

mission time and improvements in overall coverage quality, contributing directly to the project's performance KPIs. Simulation activities will be expanded, and preparations will begin for real-world validation in collaboration with Task 3.4, ensuring that the planner performs reliably under operational conditions.

At the interface level, the user interface will be refined to move from its initial version to a fully developed mission-configuration and visualization tool. Improvements will focus on usability, clearer parameter settings, and seamless interaction with backend services. Additionally, the work will concentrate on ensuring that all planned refinements explicitly support project-level KPIs, strengthening the contribution of this task to the overall iDriving objectives.

The final phase will involve full system integration and end-to-end workflow testing with the relevant WP3 components. This will confirm operational readiness and ensure that the UAV mission planner performs effectively within the complete iDriving ecosystem. Through these steps, this task will transition from a functional prototype to a mature, optimized, and fully validated module ready for deployment in the project's demonstration scenarios.

8 Conclusions

8.1 Main results to date

Deliverable D3.1 presents the first integrated version of the components developed under Work Package 3, demonstrating significant progress toward establishing the V2I communication, aerial monitoring, and route optimisation capabilities required by iDriving. The work carried out across the five tasks has laid down the technical foundations for a real-time, interoperable, and safety-oriented system.

Task 3.1 has delivered the initial version of the communication architecture, defining the principles for low-latency data exchange, semantic interoperability, and data sovereignty through the use of IDSA-aligned concepts and a Vocabulary Hub. Task 3.2 has developed early prototypes of the Intelligent Traffic Management System, demonstrating the ability to analyse heterogeneous data sources and generate safety-driven traffic strategies. Task 3.3 has produced the first version of the mobile and in-vehicle applications, capable of retrieving real-time hazard information from the iDriving ecosystem and providing early warnings to different categories of road users. In parallel, Task 3.4 has advanced the aerial surveillance subsystem, delivering initial implementations of onboard sensing, embedded processing, and data streaming capabilities based on the mission UAV architecture. Finally, Task 3.5 has produced a functional prototype of the UAV mission planner, supporting complete area-coverage path planning for both single-UAV and multi-UAV missions, integrated with the platform through a Kafka-based communication layer.

Together, these developments establish the core technical elements required for V2I communication, intelligent traffic management, early-warning delivery, and UAV-based monitoring. The v1 components frame the baseline that will be further refined, validated, and integrated in preparation for demonstrations and operational use.

8.2 Next steps and planned work for next deliverable

From this point forward, WP3 will focus on improving, optimising, and completing the functionalities required for Deliverable D3.2 and for the final iDriving demonstrations. Task 3.1 will proceed with refining the communication architecture, expanding semantic interoperability mechanisms, and finalising the Vocabulary Hub. Task 3.2 will continue developing its traffic management algorithms, with emphasis on improved robustness, scalability, and integration with live data streams. Task 3.3 will enhance the usability and stability of the mobile and in-vehicle applications, ensuring seamless communication with backend components and preparing the applications for field testing.

In addition, Task 3.4 will advance the aerial surveillance subsystem through further hardware–software integration, improved onboard analytics, and validation of the sensing pipeline with scenarios. Task 3.5 will focus on optimisation of the path-planning algorithms, enhanced workload distribution across multiple UAVs, and tighter integration with Task 3.4 to ensure fully coordinated aerial mission execution. Across all tasks, emphasis will be placed on performance optimisation, KPI alignment, simulation-based verification, and preparation for real-world demonstration activities.

These next steps will transform the currently available v1 components into a fully functional, validated, and interoperable suite of tools that collectively support the iDriving objectives and the final D3.2 deliverable.

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iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

PROJECT FACTS

Start date: 01/07/2024 **Duration:** 36M **Call:** HORIZON-CL5-2023-D6-01 **Total cost:** € 4,998,733.75 **Coordinator:** Ethniko Kentro Erevnas kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (CERTH)

iDriving Consortium

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